

The Contemporary Cambodia-U.S. Relations: An Analysis of Confrontation

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The study explores the reasons of strained relations between Cambodia and the United States. The first reason is that both governments hold different perspectives on “internal interference” term. Moreover, The Prime Minister seems personally traumatized by the past American actions (including the causes for civil war, murderous bombing, its support of Khmer Rouge resistance group, and the sanction on Phnom Penh regime in 1980s). Prime Minister Hun Sen often publicly criticized the U.S. actions, so it indicates that his hatred sentiments over the U.S. government exist, all of which impact the communication between leaders of both countries and the bilateral relation. The second reason is that the US foreign policy miscalculation has alienated Cambodian government. Thus, Prime Minister Hun Sen and his ruling party see China as a reliable friend who can share mutual benefits and respects. Moreover, even Cambodia strives to enlarge cooperation with the United States, some U.S. politicians still has negative mentality on Cambodia regarding its closed relations with China, but actually Cambodia have struggled to balance between these two superpowers. Third reason is about shared interests; it means that sour relation between Cambodia and the United States is resulted from the lack of strategic interests. If Cambodia has strategic or economic interests for the U.S., the criticism on human rights could be vanished, and when there is no allegation or sanction related to Human Rights, both governments would cooperate better.

Keywords: COOPERATION, CONFRONTATION, HISTORICAL ANALYSIS

Introduction

Despite far geographical distance, Cambodia and the United States established diplomatic relations in 1950 when the wave of colonization resistance emerged globally. It was 3 years earlier before Cambodian gained Independence from French. In 60s, 70s and 80s, relations between the two countries were completely influenced by the Cold War and the U.S. involvement in Vietnam War, which led to confrontation and diplomatic suspension. Cambodia has undergone tragedy of civil war, and foreign invasion, all of which the United States has been involved. The differences of political characteristics led the small country like Cambodia to inevitably fall prey of the proxy war led by the United States. Even in the 21st century, both countries have very little time to enjoy harmonious relations together. The difference is normal in bilateral

relation; even alliances also have divergent views. Even though Cambodia and the United States share fruitful cooperation in multi-faceted areas, in both bilateral and multilateral framework, some differences on various issues remain and it has led to troubled relation. Tensions in Cambodia-U.S. relations from 2017 have been triggered as results of the differences on many areas including human right, wartime debt, Chinese military presence allegation, and Cambodian national deportation, as presented below. The setback in one area of cooperation could negatively influence other areas.

2020 marks the 70th anniversary of Cambodia-US relations, which is therefore a suitable time to examine the relations that have gone through ups and downs. The relation between Cambodia and the US remains not so good, and not so bad. In international relation, it is difficult and there is no equipment like scale or tape measure to make exact measurement of the extent of relation between one and another country. The above-said assessment of relation was given by taking into account of the level of cooperation, diplomatic interaction, common interests and the areas of divergence. The Washington's concerns on civil liberal space, democracy and human rights issues in Cambodia cause sour bilateral relations. Plus, China's growing influence in Cambodia always irritated Cambodia-US relations, in similar patterns that the US was always irritated by the neutrality of King Sihanouk four decades ago. It seems that the issues responsible for deteriorating relations can be identified, but the solution can not be reached. It is important to raise one question that why both countries could not put the problem on the table to discuss and resolve it. Cambodia is just a small and developing country, so why Cambodia does not bridge its relations with the United States and takes advantages from the US, instead of causing troubled relations. There surely be some implications.

I. Key confrontational issues

Human rights and democracy

In September 2017, Mr. Kem Sokha, the leader of opposition CNRP Party, was arrested for treason charge for conspiring with the United States to topple the legitimate government with Color Revolution. The government perceived that the color revolution is kind of protest to overthrow the legitimate government born from democratic election, so this kind of protest would cause social and political instability and disorder and violate the Kingdom's constitution. From Mr. Kem Sokha's video shared in Facebook, he publicly stated that the United States has given him several instructions to succeed in regime change. He was told to leave the politics for a while to form an NGO working on human rights and he was introduced and trained on leadership change based on the approach taken in former Yugoslavia. The government change in Yugoslavia was not through democratic election but street protests. The Cambodian Government viewed that the arrest did not intend to undermine democratic space but to enforce the rule of law and to protect the sovereignty of Cambodia as well as to maintain peace and stability.

Two months after the detention of opposition leader, in November, the Supreme Court of Cambodia issued a final verdict to dissolve the biggest opposition party, CNRP, and banned 118 CNRP membered from engaging

in political activities for five years, based on the accusation that the party was plotting conspiracy with foreign powers to topple the legitimate government in the form of color revolution. The government explained the dissolution was decided by the existing law of the country and wholly in the jurisdiction of judicial power. The move did not mean to kill the political system of pluralistic liberal democracy and the three million vote of CNRP supporter. Instead, it was the protection of the rights and will of the more than 4-million voters supporting the ruling party, who always want social order, political stability and the rule of law.

To respond to what the United States consider as the cause of human right abuses in Cambodia, the US government, as well as the Congress, have endorsed and proposed many bills and orders to sanction Cambodian individuals and entities. The primary sanction is implemented under the Global Magnitsky Human Rights Accountability Act on which the US Department of Treasury, in 2018 and 2019, sanctioned General Hing Bun Hieng, General Kun Kim, tycoon Try Pheap, including their family member and companies linked to them. The sanction will block all their properties within the US jurisdiction. Moreover, the US Congress approved the Consolidated Appropriations Act in 2018 to impose conditions upon U.S. assistance to the Government of Cambodia related to democracy and regional security. The act mandated funds for democracy programs and programs in the Khmer language to counter the influence of the People's Republic of China in Cambodia.¹ In addition, in 2017, the US government announced that it would restrict entry into the US of those individuals involved in undermining democracy in Cambodia. This sanction was expanded until now.

Besides the U.S. lawmakers have attempted to propose a series of bills in order to impose financial and Visa sanctions on high-ranking officials of the Government of Cambodia. For example, in December 2019, the US senators introduced Cambodia Democracy Act of 2019 which required US Department of State and Department of Treasury to impose sanction –asset blocking, and visa restriction – to senior Cambodian officials of the government, military and security forces, who have undermined democracy or committed related human rights violations. Another bill is Cambodia Accountability and Return on Investment Act (CARI), which requires the freezing of the wealth of Cambodian government officials who keep bank accounts in the U.S. and demand the U.S. to object all loans to Cambodia. It also requires Cambodia to protect its sovereignty from Communist China's meddling in its internal affairs. In January the same year, the United States lawmakers introduced Cambodian Trade Act of 2019 that would require a report on the continuing participation of Cambodia in the US Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) program, which provides duty-free treatment on some Cambodian exports to the United States. Another important act,

¹ Lum TG. Cambodia: background and U.S. relations in brief Washington, DC: Congressional Research Service; 2019.

Cambodia Democracy Act of 2018 comes with a list of individual's subjects to the sanctions. The list consists of senior Cambodian officials who have allegedly committed or directed severe human rights violations associated with undermining democracy in Cambodia, including Prime Minister Hun Sen and Foreign Minister. It required the US Department of State and Department of Treasury to impose sanction by applying asset blocking and visa entry restriction. Furthermore, none of the bill has ever become the law. The process to endorse a law requires a lot of attention from boss Congress and White House, so the problems in Cambodia might not be prioritized. It is was proposed with the purpose of signaling to Government of Cambodia that the United States is concerning on the evolvement of political and human rights situation in Cambodia. However, the proposed bill strongly deteriorates the bilateral relations, and widens the misunderstanding between Phnom Penh and Washington.

Foreign military base

It is alleged that Cambodia allowed the construction of Chinese military base at its coastal area at Ream Naval Base and Dara Sakor in Koh Kong Province. First, in 2018, there was the allegation that the US \$3.8 billion development project under Chinese company Union Development Group, in Dara Sakor, Koh Kong province, was used for dual purposes including to host Chinese military base. The development project consists of condominiums, resorts, hotels, manufacturing facilities, a deep-water port, and an international airport.² Second, in 2019, The Wall Street Journal report claimed that China had signed a secret agreement allowing its armed forces to use a Cambodian Ream Naval Base, in Sihanouk province on the Gulf of Thailand.³ The deal allows 30 years of exclusive access for Chinese troops, with an automatic renewal every 10 years afterwards. In July 2019, Cambodian government denied the US offers to restore training facility and boast depot in the Base, which fueled the rumor.

In 2018, Vice-President Mike Pence wrote a letter to Prime Minister Hun Sen to express concerns on the Chinese military presence report; the Prime Minister responded that Cambodia strictly adheres to the Constitution that prohibits any military presence on its soil. Cambodia does not need any military intervention to defend itself nor to wage war against anyone.⁴ In ASEAN Foreign Ministerial Meeting in Bangkok 2019, U.S. Secretary of State Mike Pompeo said that the United States welcomes Cambodia's strong defense of its national sovereignty, and encourages other nations in the region to follow Cambodia's lead in protecting it.

² David Hutt and Shawn W. Crispin. Cambodia at the center of a new Cold War [Internet]. Asia Times. 2020 [cited 2021Jun15]. Available from: <https://asiatimes.com/2018/11/cambodia-at-the-center-of-a-new-cold-war>

³ Page J, Lubold G, Taylor R. Deal for Naval Outpost in Cambodia Furthers China's Quest for Military Network [Internet]. The Wall Street Journal. Dow Jones & Company; 2019 [cited 2021Jun15]. Available from: https://www.wsj.com/articles/secret-deal-for-chinese-naval-outpost-in-cambodia-raises-u-s-fears-of-beijings-ambitions-11563732482#comments_sector

⁴Name. Cambodia's PM Hun Sen Denies Reports of Plans For Chinese Naval Base [Internet]. Radio Free Asia. 2020 [cited 2021Jun15]. Available from: <https://www.rfa.org/english/news/cambodia/base-11192018155126.html>

Chinese military allegation is one of the most sensitive issues and Prime Minister Hun Sen, Cambodian foreign ministers as well as Defense ministers, have repeatedly address and clarify the issue. There is no answer whether the rumor is true or not. However, the Government of Cambodia has invited diplomatic corps, foreign friends, media and NGOs to visit both places. The allegation does not end, even after a series of explanation both publicly and privately. In 2020, the issue is triggered again after the US-funded building was demolished. In East Asia Summit 2020, Robert O' Brien, the US National Security Advisor still voice its concerns that Cambodia plans to host a foreign navy and its personnel in Ream Naval Base, which will undermine the maritime security in the region.

Cambodian national deportation

From 2002 until January 2020, Cambodia received 768 deportees who are Cambodian nationals convicted of a felony crime. Many of them came to the US during the 1980s as refugee children, and never have lived in Cambodia or had left since they were too young. Many Cambodian subjects to deportation have jobs and families in the US, and many served already in prison in the US for the crime they committed. Under the Trump Administration, the rising of Cambodia nationals receiving the order of removal increased. At the same time, the government of Cambodia, in 2017, decided to suspend receiving deportees and requested to amend the 2002 MoU on Repatriation based on the compassionate grounds. The Cambodian nationals subject to deportation have very little knowledge of Cambodia, cannot speak the Khmer language, or even have no relatives living in Cambodia. Those returnees cannot find a job, lack of social communication, and barely make a living in Cambodia. As results, some of them turned mentally sick or even committed suicide. Cambodia viewed that Cambodia and the United States have inflicted double punishment on them.

However, the Department of Homeland Security deemed that the Cambodian government was uncooperative and hindering US deportation efforts and finally placed Cambodia on a list of recalcitrant countries. The U.S. government imposed limited visa restrictions upon Cambodian Foreign Ministry employees and their families. It was such a coercive stance to enlarge the mistrust gap without diplomatic manners. In retaliation, Cambodian Government viewed the move was unacceptable and claimed that even the visa restriction did not affect its officials, but it could send the wrong message and painted bad picture on Cambodia to the world. Finally, the government of Cambodia decided to suspended humanitarian cooperation with the United States on finding the US soldier remains during the Vietnam War (POW/MIA). Shortly afterwards, the government of Cambodia agreed to restart the deportation process while the US consented to provide rehabilitation support to deportees arriving in Cambodia.

Military cooperation suspension

In 2017, the Cambodian government suspended Angkor Sentinel, an annual bilateral military exercise launched in 2010 that focuses on international peacekeeping, humanitarian assistance, and military-to-military cooperation. This military exercise is the only productive and the biggest for the military-to-military

cooperation of the two countries. The reason given from the government is that Cambodia was preparing for the communal election and anti-illegal-drug campaign. However, some observers interpreted the unilateral action as a sign of Hun Sen's further distancing the Kingdom from the United States.⁵

The Cambodian government also postponed the U.S. Navy Mobile Construction Battalion, the U.S. humanitarian mission, without an explanation indefinitely. The program had worked with the Cambodian army since 2008 and provided more than \$5 million to implement community service projects throughout the country.⁶

Debt

Another important constraint for the development of bilateral relations is Cambodia's wartime debt to the United States. Background of the debt is that it occurred during the years of early 1970s, during which the government of the Khmer Republic Regime (coup d'état King Sihanouk) signed a credit agreement with the U.S in the form of commodity purchase.⁷ The United States and Cambodian governments continually challenge the differences of debt which now has accumulated over USD 500 million, including interests and penalties. The negotiation is stalled at some points.

From the Cambodian Government's perspective, the debt should be cancelled, as Cambodia has never obtained any compensation for the US' bombing, which killed hundreds of thousands of Cambodians during 1970s for the U.S. geopolitical interests. Cambodia requested the cancellation of the debts or turned the debt into development aids because Cambodia considered it as dirty debts and some commodities never reached Cambodia.

The United States government has cancelled some portions for which there is a lack of documentation and waived some amount of interests. The US has proposed to reduce the loan or reschedule payments, but only if Cambodia agrees to sign a bilateral debt agreement, which the current government has refused. The U.S. officials have clarified that debt relief could not be approved due to the current Cambodia's relatively low debt-to-GDP ratio and its fiscal ability to repay the debt.

⁵ Pike J. Military [Internet]. III MEF Exercises. [cited 2021Jun15]. Available from: <https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/ops/angkor-sentinel.htm>

⁶ Reaksmey H, Khmer VOA. Cambodia Cancels U.S. Military Aid Program as China Ties Expand [Internet]. VOA. Cambodia Cancels U.S. Military Aid Program as China Ties Expand; 2017 [cited 2021Jan21]. Available from: <https://www.voacambodia.com/a/cambodia-cancels-us-military-aid-program-as-china-ties-expand/3799123.html>

⁷ Mony S, Khmer VOA. Resolution of Wartime Debt Remains Challenge, Potential Key to Improving US-Cambodia Ties, Analysts Say [Internet]. VOA. Resolution of Wartime Debt Remains Challenge, Potential Key to Improving US-Cambodia Ties, Analysts Say; 2020 [cited 2021Mar7]. Available from: <https://www.voacambodia.com/a/resolution-of-wartime-debt-remains-challenge-potential-key-to-improving-us-cambodia-ties-analysts-say-/5571101.html>

II. Implications of the Confrontation

The perspective of non-interference and shadow of history as the cause of mistrust

In April 2017, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Cambodia quoted the speech of Mr. Ron Paul, former US Congressman “it is not democracy to send in billions of dollars to push regime change overseas. It is not democracy to send in the NGOs to rewrite laws”.⁸ The Ministry attempted to publicly explain that the United States was the most significant agent for regime change in foreign countries by funding and supporting civil society as its tool. In the United Nations General Assembly in 2018, Prime Minister addressed that we are regretful to underline that nowadays human rights have become a mission to impose civilization for some powerful nations or, perhaps, as their operating standards as the pretext for interference under the name of political right protection.⁹

The United States provided millions of dollars to promote human rights, democracy, and good governance in Cambodia. Those assistances have channeled to various NGOs, which always criticizes the government and explicitly work closely with the opposition party. The Government of Cambodia considers the criticism from NGOs as the campaign of disinformation to exacerbate minor problems and to provide twisted, double-standard and biased information, in order to discredit and defame the governmental institutions. The US lawmakers and Department of States frequently expressed their concerns of human rights, civil society and democracy situation in Cambodia, alleged the government of Cambodia of their so-called political suppression and urged for sanctions on senior government officials. In response, not only once, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Cambodia repeatedly released its press statement to provide clarification to the allegations from Washington. From various press statement of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, it is possible to assume that the Government of Cambodia believes that the policymakers in Washington solely believed and cited the information provided through their sponsored NGOs, which is biased to the opposition party and ignore all factual and legal explanation provided by the government. Moreover, the Government of Cambodia had suspects of the foreign attempt to intervene in Cambodian internal affairs to make regime change by color revolution. There is no any study by now to verify that whether the United States truly seeks for regime change in Cambodia or not. However, the truth is that many US congress members and politicians strongly condemned Prime Minister Hun Sen and his ruling parties for decades. Another truth is that Prime Minister Hun Sen is truly concerned of any opposition movement against the government supported by foreign powers. The Government of Cambodia’s perspective might be that the operation and sponsor of NGOs in the country

⁸ Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation. To Tell the Truth: Cambodia, Democracy and Human Rights. Government Publication, Phnom Penh: MFA-IC; 2017.

⁹ Thul PC. Cambodia's Hun Sen says will give speech to U.N. after 'flawed election' [Internet]. Reuters. Thomson Reuters; 2018 [cited 2021Apr21]. Available from: <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-cambodia-politics-United-nations-idUSKBN1KR0IV>

is the preparing step at grassroots for regime change one day when the time permits. Any revolution against the democratic norm will end up destroying the hard-earned peace and stability that Cambodia has just enjoyed for a few decades. Thus, it means that both government hold different perspective on internal interference term. The Government of Cambodia perceives that the US always supported opposition group in Cambodia in order to change the incumbent government, while the U.S. perceives that their action is to help build democracy in the country.

The shadow of history

The relations between the two countries seem to be weighed in by the historical baggage which disrupts the potentially productive collaboration. Looking back to the history, in 1960s the King Father Norodom Sihanouk deeply concerned of the US intention to topple him. Then, in March 1970, Coup ousted him and a new US-aligned regime, Khmer Republic, was established which later led to civil war and ended up in Khmer Rouge regime. It is undeniable that the US involvement was a big part to push Cambodia to civil war, genocidal regime and immeasurable destruction of the country. Not only being a cause of pushing the Khmer Rouge forward, the United States at the end of the day decided to abandon Khmer Republic to the criminal hand Khmer Rouge. According to the letter of Prince Sirimatak¹⁰ and the interview of US Ambassador Dean¹¹, both clearly illustrated how the U.S. abandoned one regime, backed or installed by itself, without any regret or guilt. Learning of the history, Cambodian leader strongly believes that the United States could never be trusted as a reliable friend, who always comes with hidden agenda. Any single doubtful engagement of the United States with the opposition party, and NGOs could not be ignored; otherwise, the country could be fall in the same path in the history in 1970.

Furthermore, Prime Ministry Hun Sen had hatred sentiments with the United States since his youth in 1970s. After the toppling of King Sihanouk, he was one of the youths fleeing into the forest to support Khmer Rouge force in order to fight Lon Nol Regime. His decision was motivated by the American hatred on its bombing, aggression into Cambodia, and its back to overthrow the King Father Sihanouk.¹² Even in public speech, Prime Minister Hun Sen always mentioned about the U.S. bombing and how it killed Cambodian lives, and destroyed the country. He also refers the United States' allegation on the presence of Chinese military in Cambodia as the trick with ill intention on him. He said that it has been so annoying that some foreign countries tried to heat up the situation even I and my colleagues already explained many times. Then he reminded of the US-supported coup to oust the King Father Sihanouk using the pretext of combatting Viet

¹⁰ Before the Holocaust: The End of Cambodia. [cited 2021Jun1]. Available from: <http://www.edwebproject.org/sideshow/history/end.html>

¹¹ Gray DD. Ambassador: US handed Cambodia to 'butcher' 40 years ago [Internet]. AP NEWS. Associated Press; 2015 [cited 2021Mar29]. Available from: <https://apnews.com/article/a497c657b5ff4cf5938ee42cb16733ab>

¹² Author Tarr Chou Meng. A Talk with Prime Minister Hun Sen [Internet]. Cultural Survival. 1990 [cited 2021Feb11]. Available from: <https://www.culturalsurvival.org/publications/cultural-survival-quarterly/talk-prime-minister-hun-sen>

Cong in Cambodian territory. “Now, what is your intention towards me when you keep talking about the presence of the Chinese military.”¹³

Moreover, even after ousting Khmer Rouge, Hun Sen becomes Prime Minister in the 1980s. The United States did not recognize his regime, imposed embargoes, and isolated Cambodia from receiving international development. The US also supported Khmer Rouge seat in the UN and the remaining Khmer Rouge forces along the Cambodia-Thai borders. All of these facts cause a big trauma for Prime Minister Hun Sen and members in his inner circle, because they perceived that it was a very dangerous and difficult mission to win war against Khmer Rouge and take control back on Phnom Penh, but the United States still recognized Khmer Rouge and sanctioned them instead. During that time, what Cambodia needed the most was foreign assistance because everything was destroyed by Khmer Rouge, but the United States provided embargoes. Khmer Rouge was the biggest Human Rights violator, but it was ignored by the United States for years, but now the government of Cambodia which brings peace to the country is criticized with Human Rights violation frequently. Given all of these reasons, it seemed that history has partially impacted on the incumbent leader mindset when interacting with the United States. Prime Minister was seen aggressively responded to the US critics and sometimes stated anti-American sentiments when he gave a speech in the public event. It is like the wind that easily burn out the straw.

U.S. perspective on China’s influence in Cambodia

Many studies have found that the United States is tepid with Cambodia because Cambodia is seen as the closest ally of China in the region. The United States might perceive that the series of criticism and proposed sanction on Cambodia is to alert other countries that anyone is getting close to China will have to confront with the United States. It remains the question of whether it is true or not that the US seeks to cause strained relations with Cambodia for this reason, which will be explained below.

First, Cambodia foreign policy is moved in the direction that could please both powers, China and the United States, due to their great significance to the Kingdom’s security and economy. Regarding relations with China, Cambodia is the strong supporter of One China Policy and Belt and Road Initiative. Phnom Penh’s strong relation with Beijing is not developed at the expense of its relationship with Washington. Cambodia has indeed extended positive gestures towards Washington on multiple occasions. For example, Cambodia has strong support to the United States in multiple regional initiatives including ASEAN and Lower Mekong framework. Cambodia is the strong supporter to the US’s MIA programs to explore the remaining of American soldiers during Vietnam War before the beginning of diplomatic re-establishment. Moreover, in February 2020, at the request from the United States, Cambodia immediately agreed to allow Westerdam

¹³Office of the Council of Ministers of Cambodia. Selected Comments Samdech Techo Hun Sen, at the Groundbreaking Ceremony to Build Bridges from Koh Pich to Koh Norea and from Koh Norea to National Road 1. 2020. [cited 2021Jun1]. Available from: <https://pressocm.gov.kh/en/archives/67944>.

Cruise Ship, on board of which there were more than 2000 people including 600 Americans, to dock in its sea after the ship was denied by five territories and island due to their fear of Covid-19 transmission. It is another indication of Cambodia's move to restore cooperation and trust with United States through humanitarian gestures after years of relations friction. In addition, in response to the US's concerns over the Chinese military base in Cambodia coastal area, Cambodian government invited foreign observers including American diplomats, other foreign diplomatic corps in Phnom Penh, journalists and NGO personnel to eye witness where the United States had suspected. In military front, Cambodia is always intent to enhance bilateral defense cooperation with the U.S. and aspire for the U.S. assistance and involvement in its military modernization process. Despite all of these positive cooperation, some US leaders and lawmakers keep holding negative mentality over Cambodia-Sino relations and this mentality has continued to erode the mutual trust and understanding between the United States and Cambodia.

Second, after liberation from Khmer Rouge, Prime Minister Hun Sen drove Cambodian foreign policy, being a close friend with Vietnam and Soviet Union (1980s regime was backed by Vietnam and Vietnam troops presented in Cambodia). In 1993, after the first general election, Hun Sen is still the Prime Minister of Cambodia, so Vietnam is still a traditional close ally of the government of Cambodia. Comparing Cambodia-US relation and Cambodia-China relation under the Prime Minister Hun Sen in 1993, both Cambodia-US and Cambodia-China relations are at the same level (the starting point) because the United States and China did not have direct formal relations with Prime Minister Hun Sen before the 1993 election. Starting from the same position, Sino-Cambodia now reaches its peak of relation as the comprehensive strategic partnership. In contrast, Phnom Penh and Washington share a handful of different perspective over the years and eventually, tension arises unprecedentedly. Actually, since 1993 the US assistance had been granted to rehabilitate the socio-economy in the country, to provide basic needs to Cambodian people, and to help isolate and integrate Khmer Rouge forces. All of these facts depicted the US commitment to restoring a healthy relationship with Cambodia. However, the United States simultaneously brought disturbance and criticism to Phnom Penh government over authoritarianism and corruption, while at that time Cambodia had prioritized ensuring food security, maintaining social order and speeding Khmer Rouge integration, rather than focusing on those American ideal of democracy and human rights. The United States has to understand that democracy could not be injected into Cambodia and expects Cambodia to conduct perfectly immediately. From year to year, the US increasingly criticize Hun Sen government, and Prime Minister Hun Sen gradually maneuvered Cambodian foreign policy away from the United States, and increasingly approached Beijing for aids and economic cooperation because Chinese assistance is in line with the principles of Cambodian government of non-interference and respect of sovereignty.

Therefore, it can be said the United States made a miscalculation on its policy toward Cambodia by attempts to injecting human rights and democracy in the time that Cambodia needed the most was only peace and food.

The United States also push Cambodia getting closer and closer to China by itself. Maybe in 1990s, with its sole hegemony, the United States might not expect that one day it will have to confront with China like today, so the United States might not expect small developing states, like Cambodia, could choose other besides the U.S. itself. Thus, it is because the U.S. foreign policy itself that is problematic. The United States foreign policies itself that have pushed Cambodia further becoming one of the strong allies with China.

Taking geopolitics and economic interests into consideration, it is unquestionably true that Cambodia could not choose the United States over China; not necessary to provide much data to prove it. Just referring to Chinese assistance, investment and loan, it is enough to explain Cambodia should embrace China for its advantages. However, if, since the start, the United States carefully engaged and did not toughly pressured Cambodian government, the United States might be able to seize more spaces to attract Cambodia towards Washington.

Looking to other corner, if the US continues its current tough policy, it is probably not a good choice as it provides little incentive for Cambodia to alter its political position. Looking at Japan as example, Japan has watched the development of Sino-Cambodian relations closely; however, Japan has avoided all forms of any actions that can provoke diplomatic tension with Cambodia, partially because of its non-confrontational diplomatic norms.¹⁴ Japan might perceive that tougher diplomacy will likely be counterproductive and push Cambodia closer to China.

US's interests in Cambodia

It is important to note that Cambodia and the United States never had the history of harmony relations since its first day until now, except during the US-backed regime, Khmer Republic. In the 1960s and 70s, the US's interests in Indochina was not about Cambodia or Laos, but it was entirely about Vietnam. The United States did not pay much attention to King Sihanouk's concerns of Cambodian sovereignty and territory. One concrete evidence was the carpet bombing, made without the consent and knowledge of the US Congress. In 1975, the United States deserted the Khmer Republic regardless of what Cambodian people would face, just only after North Vietnam prepared to gain victory, meaning that there was no more US interest in Indochina after losing war in Vietnam. After 1993 election in Cambodia, the US, perhaps, still did not see any interests in Cambodia and kept choosing the human rights agenda to humiliate the current government of Cambodia, even doing so could only deteriorate Cambodia-US relations. Thus, it remains an important question to find out that whether there are any economic or strategic interests in Cambodia-US relations or not.

¹⁴ PacNet #43 - US-Cambodia Relations: Growing Strategic Mistrust? [Internet]. All-In-One Integrated Marketing Platform for Small Business. [cited 2021Jun2]. Available from: <https://mailchi.mp/pacforum/pacnet-43-us-cambodia-relations-growing-strategic-mistrust-keenynxh5j?e=1a9f93dadd>

The trade volume of both countries is increasing, but it is the trade deficit for the US. There is also no US military base in its territory (Cambodia Constitution does not allow to do so), while military cooperation is in tiny scale. Cambodia and the United States cooperate in wide ranges of areas but it is still minimal and do not show strategic convergence. Cambodia received billion-dollar assistances from the United States to rebuild the country. Even though the relation and cooperation between the two countries keep progressing in a very moderate manner, there has never been any noticeably extraordinary cooperation, compared to that of the United States with other countries in the region like Singapore, Thailand or Vietnam.

Cambodia might hold political interest for the United States, given the status of Cambodia as the member of ASEAN. ASEAN also provides a platform that the US could play a role in the regional security and to maintain its interests in the region. The United States views ASEAN centrality and consensus as the significant value. This interest keeps the United States seeking ways to engage with Cambodia. If there is no Cambodia voice there would be no consensus for ASEAN. If Cambodia prioritizes its bilateral relations with China over the ASEAN's collective interests, it would inhibit the US regional engagement in a regional issue.

Regarding the geo-politic and strategic interests, one scenario of four variables – Cambodia, China, Vietnam and the United States – has to be explained. First, China needs Cambodia for its regional geopolitical strategy and provides Cambodia economic and strategic advantages. While Vietnam remains the biggest external threat, which used to share bitterly complex history in the last three centuries with Cambodia. Some Cambodians have viewed Vietnam as threat, seeking to encroach on the sovereignty of Cambodia. In this context, China becomes the most important strategic partner for Cambodia to check Vietnam if it chooses to pursue the expansionist policy over the Kingdom. Therefore, Cambodia-China relation is the strategic relation, while Cambodia-Vietnam is the most cautious relation that needs to be balanced to protect national security. Second, Vietnam and the United States share strategic relations that both countries have to confront China. The more the US getting closer to Vietnam, the more Cambodia has to worry about its security. From this scenario, it clearly illustrates that Cambodia and the United States do not share any significant strategic interests.

Another important argument is that human rights and democracy would never be the problem of the two countries' relation. Although, Cambodia conducts democratic and recognized election every 5 years, the Cambodian Government has always been suffered from the human rights and democracy criticism from Washington. Cambodia host more than thousand NGOs in the country, and allow thousand newspaper and online media houses to operate freely, some of which are critical to the government. However, the communist country like Vietnam, and junta government in Thailand was rarely condemned. Since the reestablishment of diplomatic relations between the United States and Vietnam in 1995, both countries share cooperative and comprehensive relations and developed their relationship status to Comprehensive Partnership in 2013. Top

leaders of both countries made frequent visit including the official visit of President Bill Clinton, George W Bush, Barack Obama, and Donald Trump to Vietnam. It means that human rights and democracy are just the pretexts, when there are common interests between the two sides. There is not only an example of the United States but the European Union to decide to revoke the tariff privileges, *Everything But Arms* (EBA), from products imported from Cambodia. But at the same time, the EU signed a free trade agreement with Vietnam. Cambodia is always on the agenda of human rights violation and freedom suppression of the West because Cambodia does not have economic or strategic interest for the West. Because there is no actual interest either one of military, economy or politic, the United States will not want to engage deeply and revitalize the relations with Cambodia. Therefore, Cambodia has not much option but to continue seeing China as the most reliable partner, whose friendship is the most traditional, sincere, amicable and fruitful.

Materials and methods

This article is an in-depth qualitative research of the relations between Cambodia and the United States. The research is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data collected from official governmental webpage from relevant countries such as Cambodia, and the United States. While the secondary data are from various academic books, journals, scholarly articles, and academic research papers, to analyze and synthesize the finding of the research. Importantly, content from website of Cambodian Foreign Ministry and US Department of States are the most important sources for the research in order to reflect the view of both governments. Media like newspaper and opinion article is also important because it provides the most recent information, new timeline of relations and any updated world situation that related to the topic. However, views from scholars and independent analyst cannot be ignored because it provides insight as the third party in the form of academia.

Conclusion

Cambodia and the United States have some divergent views which led to confrontation. There are several incidents since 2017 such as the arrest of opposition leader, the dissolution of opposition party, Cambodian national deportation issues, allegation on foreign military base, and debt negotiation. Washington has begun to propose plenty of bills in order to sanction Cambodian senior governmental officials with asset frozen and visa ban. At the same time, the US unilaterally imposed visa sanction on Foreign Affairs' officials due to the suspension of deportation. The US administration alleges that Cambodia has accepted Chinese military presence on its soil. Even Cambodian leaders have explained and clarified in every available occasion, but the problem persists. Another thorny issue of Debt is also going on for decades without any resolution. All of these problems, new and old, have impeded relations from growing stronger. Moreover, Cambodian senior leaders' concern of intervention and suspicion on the U.S. intention is true. Historical implication that the United States has brought tragedy to Cambodia affects Cambodian senior leaders' ways of thinking toward the United States. Secondly, U.S. concern of China influence in Cambodia is resulted from the miscalculation

of U.S. foreign policy on Cambodia at the initial stage. Thirdly, the lack of economic and strategic interests has prevented both countries to improve relationship and resolve the differences.

It is possible to say that Washington perceives there are still some spaces for U.S. to maneuver to check China's influence in Cambodia. The US effort to keep engagement with Cambodia illustrates in two aspects. First, President Trump communicates with Prime Minister Hun Sen through an exchange of correspondences, stated that the U.S. never seeks regime change. The letter already depicted clearly, but what worth to wait is the exact and real action that the U.S. has to prove. Second, in 2019, Department of State appointed new U.S. Ambassador to Cambodia, Mr. Patrick Murphy, then principal deputy assistant secretary of state for the Bureau of East Asian and Pacific Affairs. The appointment of a senior official like this could be explained that the U.S. wishes to restore good relation with Cambodia after utterly deteriorating since 2017. Furthermore, a practical approach for the US would, therefore to proactively engage with the Cambodian government rather than attempting to change the status quo. Seeking rapprochement to the ruling party should choose over interventionist approach if the United States is willing to build a friendly and constructive relationship with Cambodia. Some area of differences, in particular minor problems like deportation of Cambodian nationals and debt, should be discussed and resolved without tough position like sanctions. Given that the United States considers the maintenance of a rules-based order as crucial to peace and prosperity in the region, it would be in its interest to have Cambodia on board as an active partner. This would provide more benefits than that of its attempt to make political change.

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